

Methodology and Design Consideration for Experimental Model to Formulate Analytical Equations for Manually operated Potato Peeling Machine

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Abstract: Indian food processing sector particularly potato processed product has grown strongly in recent decades and is likely to continue to expand as domestic producers increase their capacity to meet anticipated demand. The literature survey revealed the wide coverage of human power as a alternative power source to daily household and business applications. The design calculation of manually operated potato peeling machine is done. A machine has been fabricated which will perform the peeling operation not by electric power but by manual power. In this paper an approximate generalized experimental data based model for such a manual operated potato peeling machine is developed by varying some independent parameters during experimentation. This paper also reports the design of experimental setup to carry out the experimentation for establishing empirical relationship for potato peeling machine energized by human

Keywords: Human powered Flywheel Motor, manual potato peeling machine, Potato, Mathematical model ,Experimental model

I. INTRODUCTION

India achieved a tremendous growth in potato production during last five to six decades. The statistics suggest (faostat.org.com) India is amongst the leading producer of potatoes in world, precisely second and contributes to 12.5 % of global production. As stated in report of Horticulture Division, Ministry of Agriculture, Government of India, New Delhi, the area and production of potato in the country during 2017-18 is estimated around 21.51 lakhs hactores and 485.29 lakhs MT respectively. The biggest opportunity before Indian is that there is enormous scope for increasing consumption of potato in almost all sectors including the rural sector which remains fairly unexposed to the multi-faceted use of potato. Food processing industries in India have launched massive expansion/ modernization programs with a view to adopt modern technology which is energy efficient, cost effective and environment friendly. They have also shown keenness to adopt latest technologies to make existing processes more efficient and productive. Potatoes are also dehydrated in the forms of slices, sticks, cubes or powder to impart better shelf life. Another popular use is to make wafers or chips that's why potato became popular food item not in home but also in hotels, canteens, restaurant, etc. Hence peeling method of potato is point of interest.

Potato peeling by human is time consuming and tedious process and may require several workers to carry out operation which ultimately increases operating cost. Involvement of more labour and consumption of time encourage the variety of peeling methods [16]. Traditionally this operation is done with appropriate sharp knife edge by applying suitable pressure shown in figure.1. The quality of final products in market is lot more depend on peeling process stage .

Load shedding & power cuts is major problem, today India is facing. We can't use the electrical energy whenever we need due to load shedding. Therefore human power may be used for a process if the power requirement is a maximum of 76W. If power requirement is excess than 75W and if the process can be of an intermittent nature without disturbing quality of the end product, a man machine-system can be developed that stores energy. The energy sources of these types are considered as one form of energy source of non- conventional type. The needs of this work in almost all area particularly remote and interior area for energizing process unit in the range up to 5 Hp. it will be of tremendous help to poor people / people in villages, firstly because it does not need any type of conventional energy.

Fig.1 Traditional potato peeling

II. BACK-GROUND OF THE PRESENT RESEARCH

Modak J.P and his associates [1 –11]* have developed Human Powered Flywheel Motor (HPFM) energized process machines which can energize process units needing 7 to 11 hp. This machine system comprise of three subsystems (1) energy unit HPFM (2) mechanical power transmission system (3) process unit. Energy unit HPFM comprise of an arrangement similar to a bicycle, a speed raising gear pair and a flywheel. The flywheel size is one meter rim diameter 10 cm rim width and 2 cm rim thickness. A flywheel is with 6 armed constructions each arm is with elliptical cross section. Mechanical transmission comprises of spiral jaw clutch SJC and torque amplification gear pair .

Fig.2. Line Diagram of schematic arrangement of manually operated potato peeler

A young operator with a slim stature and 165cm height speeds up flywheel to 700 to 800 rpm in a minute's time. Then pedalling is stopped and SJC is engaged connecting this human powered flywheel through torque amplification gears to a process unit. The stored energy in the flywheel around 4000kgf-m gets exhausted within 10 to 15 seconds in operating a process unit depending on its process resistance. This amounts to energizing of a process unit in the range 3 to 11 hp. Recently Modak J.P has proposed the concept of when to use human powered flywheel as an energy source or on load operation of the process unit depending on the operating characteristic of the process unit [9]. In view of this, potato peeler using human powered flywheel motor as an energy source is developed. It's approximate generalized experimental data based model is evolved. This is detailed in this paper. This model is evolved applying methodology of experimentation proposed by H.Schanck, Jr [15].

III. SCOPE OF PRESENT RESEARCH

Scope is to establish design data for low to medium capacity potato peeler energized by Human Powered Flywheel Motor. With the help of this design data the specific unit for a low to medium capacity machine can be designed. The utility of such will be helpful for a small businessmen for bringing about low cost automation. As the work is ultimately useful for a low profiled businessmen in present context of lot many cases of suicide of farmers and businessmen in India. This research effort is likely to be useful in lessening the severity of this socio economic problem. Low profiled businessmen will be benefited by the proposed work. This will add to enhancement of technology for low profiled businessmen from the point of view of human powered mechanization of peeling operations.

IV. NEED FOR FORMULATING GENERALIZED EXPERIMENTAL DATA BASED MODEL

In view of foregoing it is obvious that one will have to decide what should be the minimum human energy to be supplied to the system for getting appropriate peeling of potatoes in minimum time. This would be possible if we have a quantitative relationship amongst various dependent and independent variables of the system. This relationship would be known as the mathematical model of this man machine system. It is well known that such a model for the man machine system cannot be formulated applying logic [12]. The only option with which one is left is to formulate an experimental data based model [15]. Hence, in this investigation it is decided to formulate such an experimental data based model. In this approach all the

independent variables are varied over a widest possible range, a response data is collected. Based on this data an analytical relationship is established. Once such a relationship is established, then the technique of optimization can be applied to deduce the values of independent variables at which the necessary responses can be minimized or maximized. In fact determination of

such values of independent variables is always the puzzle for the operator because it is a complex phenomenon of interaction of various independent variables such as geometric parameters of the peeling drum (drum diameter, drum length) The other parameters are lower plate diameter, clearance, size of abrasive material, size of potato, quantity of water ,gear ratio ,etc whereas the response variables would be processing time, weight of potato peeled , average resistive torque , total torque , time required to speed up flywheel .

It is well known that mathematical modelling of any complex physical system is possible applying methodology of experimentation [15]. The same is adopted in the present work.The approach adopted for formulating generalized experimental model suggested by SchenckH. Jr [15] is step wise indicated below

- 1 Identification of independent, dependent and extraneous Variables.
- 2 Reductionⁱⁱ of independent variables adopting dimensional analysis
- 3 Test planning comprising of determination of test envelope, test points, test sequence and experimentation plan.
- 4 Physical design of an experimental set-up.
- 5 Execution of experimentation.
- 6 Purification of experimental data
- 7.Formulation of the model.
8. Reliability of the Model
- 9.Model optimization
- 10.ANN Simulation of the experimental data

The first four steps mentioned above constitute design of experimentation. The seventh step constitutes model formulation where as eighth & ninth steps are respectively optimization and reliability of model. The last step is ANN Simulation of model which will precipitate most accurate model.

V. FORMULATION OF PI TERMS FOR DEPENDENT AND INDEPENDENT VARIABLES

- A. The various independent and dependent variables for manual peeling process with their symbols and dimensional formulae are given in Table 1 while Pi terms for independent and dependent variable shown in table 2.

Table 1.Variables, Symbols, Dimensional Formula

S.N	Description of variable	Type of Variable	Symb ol	Dimensio ns	S.N	Description of variable	Type of Variable	Sym bol	Dimension s
1	Flywheel energy , N-mm	Independent	E _F	M L ² T ⁻²	11	Quantity of potato ,kg	Independent	W _{PI}	M
2	Average speed of flywheel, rad/sec	Independent	W _F	T ⁻¹	12	Average size of potato,mm	Independent	d _p	L
3	Gear ratio of torque amplification	Independent	G	Dimension less	13	Modulus of elasticity of potato, N/mm ²	Independent	E _p	M ¹ L ⁻¹ T ⁻²
4	Acceleration due to gravity , m/s ²	Independent	g	LT ⁻²	14	Abrasive grid size, mm	Independent	A _Z	L
5	Modulus of elasticity of abrasive material, N/mm ²	Independent	E _A	M ¹ L ⁻¹ T ⁻²	15	Processing time of peeling	dependent	t _p	T
6	Clearance between plate and drum,mm	Independent	C	L	16	Weight of peeled potato	Dependent	W _{PO}	M
7	Diameter of	Independent	D _O	L	17	Average	dependent	T _{AV}	ML ² T ⁻²

	Drum ,mm					resistive torque on Shaft		G	
8	Length of drum ,mm	Independent	L	L	18	Total torque	Dependent	T _T	M
9	Lower plate diameter, mm	Independent	D _L	L	19	Time required to speed up flywheel	dependent	t _R	T
10	Quantity of water ,m ³	Independent	Q _w	L ³					

Table 2: Reduction of variables through dimensional analysis

Pi-term	Definition of Pi-term	Pi-zero term	Definition of Pi-zero term
π ₁	The term related energy of flywheel.	π ₀₁	The term related with Processing time (T _p)
π ₂	The term related with speed of flywheel	π ₀₂	The term related with Quantity of potato peeled (W _{p0})
π ₃	The term related with gear ratio	π ₀₃	The term related with Avg. Resistive Torque (T _{AVG})
π ₄	The term related with elasticity of material.	π ₀₄	The term related with total Torque (T _T)
π ₅	The term related to dimension of process unit.	π ₀₅	The term related with speed of flywheel during the process (t _R)
π ₆	The term related to quantity of water.		

B. Formulation of Dimensional equation

Dimensional Analysis of the parameters affecting the potato peeler energized by human powered flywheel motor was identified and listed in Table 1. Dimensional analysis was used to express the required functional relationship between the different parts of the potato peeling process. The main advantage of this analysis is the reduction of the number of variables. Dimensional equations for response variables is

1. Process time

$$t_p = k1 \sqrt{\frac{D_0}{g}} \left[\frac{E_F}{g D_0 W_{PI1}} \right]^{a1} \left[\omega_f \sqrt{\frac{D_0}{g}} \right]^{b1} [G]^{c1} \left[\frac{D_0^4 E_A E_P}{g^2 W_{PI2}} \right]^{d1} \left[\frac{C L D_L d_p A_Z}{D_0^5} \right]^{e1} \left[\frac{Q_W}{D_0^3} \right]^{f1}$$

2. Weight of output potato

$$W_{PO} = k2 W_{PI} \left[\frac{E_F}{g D_0 W_{PI1}} \right]^{a2} \left[\omega_f \sqrt{\frac{D_0}{g}} \right]^{b2} [G]^{c2} \left[\frac{D_0^4 E_A E_P}{g^2 W_{PI2}} \right]^{d2} \left[\frac{C L D_L d_p A_Z}{D_0^5} \right]^{e2} \left[\frac{Q_W}{D_0^3} \right]^{f2}$$

3. Average resistive torque

$$T_{AVG} = k3 g D_0 W_{PI} \left[\frac{E_F}{g D_0 W_{PI1}} \right]^{a3} \left[\omega_f \sqrt{\frac{D_0}{g}} \right]^{b3} [G]^{c3} \left[\frac{D_0^4 E_A E_P}{g^2 W_{PI2}} \right]^{d3} \left[\frac{C L D_L d_p A_Z}{D_0^5} \right]^{e3} \left[\frac{Q_W}{D_0^3} \right]^{f3}$$

4. Total resistive torque

$$T_T = k4 g D_0 W_{PI} \left[\frac{E_F}{g D_0 W_{PI1}} \right]^{a4} \left[\omega_f \sqrt{\frac{D_0}{g}} \right]^{b4} [G]^{c4} \left[\frac{D_0^4 E_A E_P}{g^2 W_{PI2}} \right]^{d4} \left[\frac{C L D_L d_p A_Z}{D_0^5} \right]^{e4} \left[\frac{Q_W}{D_0^3} \right]^{f4}$$

5. Time required to speed up flywheel

$$t_R = k5 \sqrt{\frac{D_0}{g}} \left[\frac{E_F}{g D_0 W_{P11}} \right]^{a5} \left[\omega_f \sqrt{\frac{D_0}{g}} \right]^{b5} [G]^{c5} \left[\frac{D_0^4 E_A E_P}{g^2 W_{P12}} \right]^{d5} \left[\frac{C L D_L d_p A_z}{D_0^5} \right]^{e5} \left[\frac{Q_W}{D_0^3} \right]^{f5}$$

C. Test Planning

This comprises of deciding test envelope, test points, test sequence and experimentation plan [15] for the deduced sets of independent pi terms.

1. Determination of Test Envelope

The test envelope comprises of complete range over which the individual independent Pi term is varied. In this test, one can calculate the ranges only for first four pi-terms. The ranges for various pi terms are ascertained and noted.

2. Determination of Test Points

The spacing of the test points within the test envelop is selected not for getting a ‘symmetrical’ and ‘pleasing’ curve but to have every part of our experimental curve mapped with the same precision as every other part. Thus, the concept of proper spacing is now replaced by permissible spacing of the test points. Similarly, for all other pi terms the test points are decided by permissible spacing rather than by the proper spacing.

3. Determination of Test Sequence

The choice of test sequence is decided by nature of experimentation viz reversible or irreversible. In fact all tests basically are irreversible in the sense that no piece of apparatus returns to an identical previous configuration after some use. But if the changes brought by testing are below the level of detection such tests could be assumed as reversible[3]. The independent variables are varied from one extreme to another in a sequential plan or in a perfectly random fashion in a random plan. The sequential plan is essential for irreversible experiments where randomization is not practicable. In this experimentation this is the case with π_3 and π_4 Pi terms .Ranges at which experiments are conducted

It is necessary to decide the range of parameters which would be varied during experimentation. The test envelope, test points and test sequence for every independent π terms

D. Procedure to conduct experiment

1. The ingredients(Kg) are poured in the Peeler drum
2. The (Human) input energy is given to the flywheel to reach its required speed
3. Clutch engage to communicate from the shaft of the flywheel to the shaft of the process unit
4. As soon as the energy is transferred the shaft of the peeler drum, peeling process start.
5. I/P & O/P speeds, time of peeling , instantaneous torque on the peeling machine shaft are measure & recorded.
6. The signals are converted into the graph which helps to get the observations which will be stored in the computer

VI. DESIGN OF EXPERIMENTAL SET UP

Design of experimental setup of Human Power Flywheel Motor includes design of various mechanical elements such as

A. Design Of Flywheel

$\Delta E =$ The maximum fluctuation of energy $= I \times k_s \times W_m^2$

Where,

I=Mass moment of flywheel

$K_s =$ Coefficient of speed fluctuation=2(metal working)

$W_m =$ Mean velocity $= \frac{W_{max} + W_{min}}{2} = \frac{15.71 + 83.73}{2} = 49.72$ rad/sec

$W_{max} = 2 \times \pi \times 150 / 60 = 15.71$ rad/sec

$W_{min} = 2 \times \pi \times 800 / 60 = 83.73$ rad/sec

Remaining dimensions of Flywheel are

h = rim thickness=20 mm, b = rim width=90 mm
 d₀ = Hub diameter=120 mm, hub width=32mm
 D₀ = diameter of flywheel=640 mm

i) Mass of Rim (M₁)= $\pi \times D_0 \times b \times t \times \rho = \pi \times 640 \times 90 \times 20 \times 7200=26.06 \text{ Kg}$
 Mass moment of inertia (I₁)= $mk^2 = 26.06 \times 0.312^2 = 2.536 \text{ Kg.m}^2$

ii) Mass of Hub(M₂) = $\pi \times 122 \times 32 \times 30 \times 7200=2.65 \text{ Kg}$
 I₂= $mk^2 = 2.65 \times 0.66 = 1.749 \text{ Kg.m}^2$

iii) Mass of Six arm (M₃) = $6 \times L \times b \times t \times \rho = 120 \times 65 \times 27 \times 7200=15.918 \text{ Kg}$
 I₃= $mk^2 = 2.653 \times 0.12=0.3183 \text{ Kg.m}^2$

Total mass of flywheel = 26.06+2.65+15.918=45 Kg
 Total M.I of flywheel(I) = 2.725+0.0063+0.3936= 3.0 Kg m²

Therefore Maximum fluctuation of energy= $\Delta E = 3 \times 2 \times 49.72^2 = 14842.35 \text{ J}$

1. Stress On Flywheel

- i).Centrifugal stress= $\rho V_s^2 = 7200(\pi \times 0.640 \times 600/60)^2 = 2.91 \text{ MPa} < 8 \text{ MPa}$ ok
 $V_s = \pi D_0 N/60 = \pi \times 0.6406 \times 600/60 = 20.16 \text{ m/sec}$
- ii) Bending stress= $\pi^2 \times V_s^2 \times \rho \times D_0 / i^2 \times h$ (Since no of arms i=6)
 $= \pi^2 \times 20.16^2 \times 7200 \times 0.64 / 36 \times 0.02 = 25.53 \text{ MPa} < 28 \text{ MPa}$ ok
- iii) Resultant stress= $0.75\sigma_1 + 0.25\sigma_2 = 0.75 \times 5.44 \times 10^6 + 0.25 \times 3.31 \times 10^{10}$
 $= 8.565 \text{ MPa} = 5 < 8.565 < 40 \text{ MPa}$ ok design for FW is safe

2. Shaft diameter of flywheel

Total K.E. in flywheel = $\frac{1}{2} I (\omega)^2$
 Total K.E. in flywheel = $\frac{1}{2} \times 3 \times (83.72)^2$
 $= 42053.08 \text{ kgf-m}$

If this energy gets exhausted in 90 sec by the process unit what is the H.P. capacity of the process unit where 1 HP = 75 kgf

$P = 42053.08/90 = 467.34/75 \text{ kgf m/s}$

$P = 6.5 \text{ HP}$

$P = 2 \pi N T/4500$

$T = \pi/16 \times f_s \times d^3$

Flywheel Shaft diameter (Shaft 2) = 40mm

B. Design Of Chain Drive

Rated power is assumed =900 W

Selecting K₁=load factor=1.2from Design Data Book

Hence Design power=Pr × K₁

=900×1.2=1080 watt

= 1.44 Hp

Selecting 1.5HP

Assume speed of smaller sprocket=120 rpm

Remaining dimensions from design data book chain no. = 50 and pitch p=15.875

Number of teeth on smaller sprocket of chain =24

Number of teeth on larger sprocket of chain =48

Pitch diameter of smaller sprocket is calculated by using formula (D_{p1})

$$= p / \sin(180/T_{\text{small}})$$

$$= 15.875 / \sin(180/24) = 121.33 \text{ mm}$$

Similarly Pitch diameter of larger sprocket is equal to 242.75 mm

Pitch line velocity= $\pi \times N \times D_s/60 = \pi \times 120 \times 21.62/60 = 0.75 \text{ m/sec}$

Power per strand= $p^2 \times [v/104 - v^{1.41}/526(26 - 25 \cos 180/T)] 10^3$

$$=15.875^2[0.764/104-0.764^{1.41}(26-25\cos180/24)]10^3$$

$$=1450.44 \text{ watt}$$

Therefore number of strand required = $1080/1453044=074=1$

Tooth Load(F_t)= $Pd/Vp=1080/0.74=1459.46 \text{ N}$

Center distance between the sprocket (C)=Diameter of larger sprocket + $1/2 \times$ smaller sprocket
 $= 242.72+1/2 \times 121.62=304 \text{ mm}$

Length of chains in pitches(L_p)= $T1+T2/2+2C/p+p(T1-T2)/40C$
 $L_p=24+48/2+2 \times 303.53/15.875+15.875 \times (48-24)/40 \times 303.53=135$

Other Dimension of Sprockets are as follows
 Outside diameter of larger sprocket = 250.73 mm
 Outside diameter of smaller sprocket = 130.1075
 Width of sprocket teeth(t_0) = $T_0=10 \text{ mm}$

C. Design Of Gear (Speed Rising Gear)

1. Design power (P_d) = $P_r \times K_1$

Selecting teeth on pinion and gear are 20 and 40 respectively

Assume rated power = $P_r = 2000 \text{ W}$

Load factor = $K_1 = 1.25$ (DDB for steady and continuous duty)

Therefore Design power (P_d) = $2000 \times 1.25 = 2500 \text{ W}$

2. Tooth load (F_t) = P_d/V_p

Pitch line velocity = (V_p) = $\pi \times D_p \times N_p/60 \times 1000$
 $= \pi \times 20m \times 900/60 \times 1000 = 0.93m \text{ m/s}$

Pitch circle diameter of pinion = (D_p) = module \times no.of teeth on pinion = $20m$

Tooth load = $2500/0.942m = 2653.9278 /m \text{ N}$ (1)

3. Bending strength (F_B) = $S_o \times C_v \times b \times Y \times m$

S_o = Assuming SAE 1045 steel with heat treatment = 210 Mpa

C_v = Velocity factor = 0.3 (Trial valve)

b = Face width of gear = $10m$ (Trial valve)

Y = Modified Lewis from factor , $Y=0.485-2.87/tp = Y = 0.485-2.87/20 = 0.35$

Therefore $F_B = 210 \times 0.3 \times 10m \times 0.3415 \times m = 215.145m^2$ (2)

After equating equation (1) and(2) module we select is equal to 3

Therefore the actual value of D_p , D_g , F_t , C_v , V_p , F_B are 60 mm, 240 mm, 885 N, 0.51, 2.82m/sec and 1936 N respectively.

As $F_B > F_t$ hence design is safe

As gear G1 is on the driving shaft and the while pinion G2 is on the flywheel shaft.

The gear ratio, $G = 80/20 = 4$

The moment of Inertia of Flywheel, $I = 3 \text{ kg-m}^2$

Angular acceleration of flywheel, $\alpha = (\omega_2 - \omega_1)/t$

Now, the value of torque to be transmitted to the pinion, Torque = $I. \alpha$

The load torque can be overcome because of the moment of inertia of flywheel = $G.I. \alpha$

$= 4 \times 3 \times 83.73 = 17.984 \text{ N-m}$.

Where

$N_1 = \omega_1 = 0$ (Initially, flywheel is at rest)

$N_2 =$ Max Speed which can be attained by flywheel = 800 rpm

$\omega_2 =$ Maximum speed attained by flywheel after peddling time $t = 60 \text{ sec}$

$\omega_2 = (2 \times 3.14 \times 800)/60 = 83.73 \text{ rad/sec.}$,

$\alpha = (83.73 - 0)/60 = 1.3955 \text{ rad/sec}^2$

Therefore maximum torque to be transmitted from gear G1 to the pinion G2 = 17.98 Nm

On vertical planes, tangential and radial forces acting on gear are calculated which helps to calculate tension in chain.

Similarly forces on horizontal plane are calculated which help to calculate the maximum bending moment and it comes out 19.66 Nm

D. Design of Shaft

Selecting Material of shaft as SAE1030 for which : $S_{yt} = 296\text{MPa}$ & $S_{ut} = 527\text{Mpa}$,

$\tau_{\max} < 0.30S_{yt}$ or $\tau_{\max} < 0.18 S_{ut}$

Therefore the design shear stress(S_{ds}) = $0.30S_{yt} = 0.30 \times 296 = 88.8\text{MPa}$

As there are provision for Keyways, design shear stress S_{ds} should be reduced by 25% and comes to 66.66 MPa

Therefore calculated diameter of shaft 1(d_1) = 20.55 mm

After considering the factors for gradually load $K_b = 1.5$ & $K_t = 1$

(Bhandari V.B.,2005; Shiwalkar B. D.,2004), recommended shaft diameter = 30

Similarly by calculations,

Diameter of shaft 2, = 25.13 mm. Selecting $D = 30$ mm.

Diameter of shaft 3, = 25.51 mm. Selecting $D = 30$ mm.

E. Design Of Bearing

Bearing For shaft 1

The horizontal and vertical components of the reactions at two bearings(P_1 and P_2) are already calculated while designing the shaft which helps to calculate dynamic load carrying capacity of bearing C_1 and C_2 .

The expected bearing life (L10) in revolution

$$L_{10} = 60 \times n \times L_{10h} / 10^6$$

Where

n = speed of rotation of shaft = 200 rpm.

L_{10h} = Expected Bearing life in hours = 20000 hours (for the machines used for eight hours of service per day)

Therefore $L_{10} = (60 \times 200 \times 20000) / 10^6 = 240$ million revolutions.

The dynamic load carrying capacity for two bearing with Load factor = 1.5 (for Chain Drive) are calculated by formula $C_1 = P_1 [L_{10}]^{1/3}$ (Load Factor) and $C_2 = P_2 [L_{10}]^{1/3}$ (Load Factor) The calculated values are 4500 N and 9000 N respectively.

For the Shaft of 30 mm diameter with above dynamic load carrying capacity, bearing 6005 is suitable and selected.

Other dimensions of the bearing:

Inner diameter of the bearing = 25 mm,

Outer diameter of the bearing = 47 mm,

Axial width of the bearing = 12 mm.

After calculation same bearing are suitable for shaft 3 and 4,

An experimental set-up for human powered potato peeler was developed and tested.

F. Dimensions of Experimental set up

1. Chain Length = 130 mm
2. Large Sprocket:
 - Diameter = 251 mm
 - Teeth = 44 mm
 - Width = 10 mm
3. Small Sprocket:
 - Diameter = 130 mm
 - Teeth = 22
 - Width = 10 mm
4. Flywheel:
 - Weight = 45 kg
 - H = Rim Thickness = 20 MM, B = Rim Width = 90 MM

- D_o = Hub Diameter=120 MM, Hub Width=32MM
 - D_o = Diameter Of Flywheel=640 MM
5. Spiral Jaw Coupling:
 - Outer diameter = 83 mm
 - Inner diameter = 25 mm
 - Width = 100mm
 6. Speed Raising Gear:
 - Weight = 6 kg
 - Pitch circle diameter = 300 mm
 - Face width = 25 mm
 - Teeth = 80
 7. Pinion:
 - Weight = 1.8 kg
 - Pitch circle diameter = 50 mm
 - Face width = 25 mm
 - Teeth = 20
 8. Shaft Dimension

Shaft 1:

 - Diameter = 30 mm
 - Length = 283 mm

Shaft 2:

 - Diameter = 40 mm
 - Length = 290 mm

Shaft 3:

 - Diameter = 30 mm
 - Length = 280 mm

Shaft 4:

 - Diameter = 30 mm
 - Length = 555 mm
 9. Three Gear Ratio -1:4,1:2.8,1:1.4

Fig 3 Developed model of manually operated potato peeler

VII. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The machine was fabricated and assembled as per design. It was found to be reliable. There were no vibrations in the set-up. The operator paddles for 1 minute, that the flywheel shaft reaches a speed of 400 RPM with a gear ratio of 1:2.8. The paddling was stopped after one minute and the set-up was checked for its free running. The flywheel came to rest after 5 minutes. It proved that the alignment of bearing and other parts of the experimental set-up was satisfactory. Thus now the experimental set-up is ready to perform the peeling of potato. .

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